

CERN EDMS 2680300

11 January 2022
a.nunezhe@cern.ch

First Irradiation test of U7-XM2 RFIDs at CERN IRRAD Facility

Alfredo María Núñez Herrero
CERN, CH-1211 Geneva, Switzerland

Keywords: CERN, irradiation experiments, irradiation facilities, IRRAD, RFID,
radio-frequency identification, radiation damage, AIDAinnova

Summary

This document shows the results of two proton irradiation experiments using radio-frequency identification (RFID) tags. It also defines an initial testing methodology to be used as reference by other irradiation facilities, with the objective of enabling the result comparison of different future related particle irradiation experiments.

Contents

1	Introduction	3
1.1	IRRAD	3
1.2	Objective	3
2	Setup	3
2.1	Chip Selection	3
2.2	IRRAD Shuttle	3
2.3	RFID Reader	4
2.4	Vertical Sample Holder	5
2.5	Sample Preparation	6
3	Methodology	8
3.1	RFID Reader & Tag Power Configuration	8
3.2	Sample Shuttle Position	9
3.3	Sample Vertical Holder Position	10
3.4	Sample Measuring Position	11
3.5	RFID Signal Strength Measurement	12
3.6	Test Parameters	12
3.7	Test Procedure	13
4	Results	14
5	Conclusions	17
6	Future Work	17
7	Acknowledgement	18

1 Introduction

1.1 IRRAD

All the irradiation tests mentioned in this document have been performed at CERN's IRRAD proton irradiation facility.

IRRAD is a proton irradiation facility located at the CERN PS East Hall. The primary proton beam is delivered from the Proton Synchrotron (PS) accelerator with a momentum of 24 GeV/c.

For more information on the IRRAD facility, see the Long Shut Down 2 Upgrade paper [1].

1.2 Objective

CAEN RFID S.r.l has provided IRRAD three different RFID chips to test their proton radiation resistance. The three chips are ALIEN Higgs-3 [2], Monza 4E [3], WINTAG U7-XM2 [4].

The project has four objectives. First, to evaluate the proton radiation resistance of the RFID chips tested. Second, to assess the damage in chips produced by proton radiation. Third, to observe any recovery of functionality after irradiations. Lastly, to define a common testing methodology across irradiation facilities to enable irradiation result comparison across different irradiation facilities and particles.

2 Setup

2.1 Chip Selection

For this initial study, only two out of the twelve RFID provided by CAEN RFID S.r.l have been tested. The reason behind their selection is their appropriateness for irradiation. The other two RFIDs were covered in additional material and needed to be stripped before being irradiated. The two chips selected are U7-XM2.

2.2 IRRAD Shuttle

This study uses the IRRAD Shuttle to perform irradiation experiments. The IRRAD Shuttle allows remote access to the irradiation area without interrupting the beam run. Figure 1 shows a picture of the IRRAD Shuttle. Figure 2 shows a picture of the sample attached to the IRRAD Shuttle ready to enter the irradiation zone.

Figure 1: IRRAD Shuttle.

Figure 2: RFID sample placed in IRRAD Shuttle for irradiation.

For more information on the IRRAD Shuttle, see the IRRAD Long Shutdown 2 (LS2) upgrade paper [1].

2.3 RFID Reader

The RFID reader used to test the tags is a HEX Multipurpose RAIN RFID Reader with model number 'R1290IE' provided by CAEN RFID S.r.l. Figure 3 shows a picture of the reader next to the vertical sample holder and sample. For more information see the reader's technical information manual [5].

Figure 3: RFID reader, sample holder and sample.

2.4 Vertical Sample Holder

To measure the signal strength emitted by the tags, a vertical sample holder has been chosen to measure the signal strength of the tag at different distance steps consistently.

Distance steps are separated by the same length, 29 mm. The last step is at a distance beyond the detection range of both tags. It is important to set this step to evaluate the initial detection capabilities of the tag before being irradiated. Figure 4 shows the sample holder and marked distance steps.

Figure 4: Sample holder and marked distance steps.

Tags might have different detection ranges, therefore it is necessary to check the limit of all the tested tags to set the last distance step beyond the maximum detection range across all tags.

2.5 Sample Preparation

The samples have been taped using Kapton to a $50 \times 50 \times 1$ mm³ layer of cardboard with a 15×15 mm² square opening in the middle to avoid the contact of the cardboard layer with the 12 mm² beam area. Figure 5 and 6 show one of the prepared samples. The RFID chip is centered in the middle of the cardboard opening.

Figure 5: RFID sample taped to cardboard layer with U7-XM2 chip centered. Front view.

Figure 6: Sample and assigned traceability ID. Back view.

3 Methodology

3.1 RFID Reader & Tag Power Configuration

For the signal strength tests, it is important to fix the power of both the reader and the tags. For this test both of them have been set to 40%. It is possible to configure both using the CAEN RFID Easy Controller Software and the reader’s web interface. For more information see the available technical information manuals [6] [7] [5].

If both configuration values aren’t maintained, it is not possible to measure consistently the tag’s signal strength. Figure 7 and 8 show the power configuration interfaces for both tag and reader.

Figure 7: RFID tag radio frequency output power configuration.

Figure 8: RFID reader input power configuration.

3.2 Sample Shuttle Position

For all irradiations, the sample has been placed in the same position with respect to the beam, with the chip and antenna facing forward to the beam as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Sample placed with and antenna facing the beam.

3.3 Sample Vertical Holder Position

Depending on where the vertical sample holder is placed, RFID signal strength values vary due to the location within the device of the radio wave emitter. For this reason, a fixed location for the sample holder has been defined for the entirety of the experiment. Figure 10 shows the position defined for the sample holder.

Figure 10: Mark of sample holder position.

3.4 Sample Measuring Position

Another condition to take into account is the position of the sample in the sample holder. A difference in signal strength values has been observed depending of the sample position in the holder. There are eight possible positions depending if the antenna is facing the ceiling or the reader and which side of the sample is inserted first on the holder. Figure 11 shows the position chosen for the test. The antenna faces the ceiling and it is placed next to the end of the slot.

Figure 11: Sample position in holder.

3.5 RFID Signal Strength Measurement

One of the measured parameters from the study is the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI). The RSSI is used to evaluate the detection range of the tag. Figure 12 shows three RFID tags and their RSSI values. The value is correlated to the distance between the tag and the reader. As an absolute value, the higher the number, the weaker the signal. Since the value is always negative, in this study it is recorded as an absolute value.

For this study, the expected behavior is to observe higher absolute values while the sample is placed in increasingly higher distance steps inside the vertical sample holder.

Regarding data acquisition, in occasions the value might fluctuate between two different values. In this case the maximum absolute value is the one recorded.

EPC	L. So...	Antenna	RSSI	COUNT	TimeStamp
E2806F12000000021F91805C	Source_0	Ant0	-525	174	22/11/2021 17:07:30
E2806F12000000021F918042	Source_0	Ant0	-545	177	22/11/2021 17:07:30
E2806F12000000021F918040	Source_0	Ant0	-525	177	22/11/2021 17:07:30

Figure 12: RFID tags and Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) highlighted in red.

3.6 Test Parameters

To perform the radiation damage and recovery assessments of samples after irradiations, multiple measurable parameters have been defined.

- **Antenna:** Test if the tag is detectable by the reader to verify if the antenna of the reader is working properly.
- **Memory integrity:** Test if the memory of the tag has changed, if any bits have varied their value as a consequence of the proton beam. For this check, not all the tag memory sections are taken into consideration. Only the user section which is the largest section with 256 bytes.
- **Reading capabilities:** Test if the tag can read values of the tag's user memory section consistently.
- **Writing capabilities:** Test if values of the user memory section can be overwritten consistently.
- **Signal strength:** Test if the detection range of the tag changes, as well as the signal strength of the tag in each distance step.

With these tests performed between each irradiation experiment, it is possible to evaluate the damage caused by the proton beam.

3.7 Test Procedure

This section defines the procedure followed for each irradiation experiment:

1. Confirm user memory section contains intended values for irradiation.
2. Test the tag before irradiation.
 - 2.1 Test if reader can detect tag. Perform at lowest distance step.
 - 2.2 Test if the user memory contains the same values as before the test. Perform at lowest distance step.
 - 2.3 Test if the RFID reader can read the same values consistently in the user memory. Perform at lowest distance step.
 - 2.4 Test if RFID reader can overwrite consistently the first 8 bytes of the user memory section. Perform at lowest distance step.
 - 2.5 Restore original memory values for first 8 bytes of user memory section. Perform at lowest distance step.
 - 2.6 Annotate maximum absolute RSSI value for each distance step.
3. Irradiate tag up to target fluence.
4. Repeat step 2 test after irradiation.

4 Results

A total of six irradiations have been performed for both tags. Three irradiations per tag. Figure 13 shows a summary of all irradiations. After the first two irradiations no damage was observed in the tags. The target fluences have been selected to match a previous study by CAEN S.r.l where tags were irradiated with gamma particles in three steps 1, 10 and 100 Gy [8]. Their study concluded tags weren't affected up to 100 Gy. As seen in Figure 13, proton and gamma irradiations results are consistent.

Regarding the planning of irradiations, for the first irradiated tag (805F), two irradiations were performed up to 10 and 100 Gy. Lastly an irradiation up to 2195 Gy. After the third irradiation the tag was unusable. For the second tag (805C), the first two irradiations were identical, and for irradiations beyond 100 Gy, the procedure was to increment step doses by a factor of 2 until tag failure. Coincidentally, only one additional irradiation of 200Gy was needed to observe tag failure.

Figure 13: Step and total accumulated absorbed dose of ionizing radiation and tag damage for irradiations performed at $20E+10$ protons per spill.

Tables 1, 2 and 3 contain all the data produced by the irradiations experiments.

Table 1 shows the irradiation's start and end timestamps for all the irradiations performed. For each irradiation there is a step and accumulated dose and a pair of timestamps indicating when the sample entered and exited the beam area. This information is useful to later verify the doses received by samples, using IRRAD's historic beam data.

Table 2 and 3 are two parts of the same table. Both tables together are the measurements checks performed to RFID tags to assess the radiation induced damage over time. The first

two columns are the ID of the tag and timestamp of measurement.

There are five measurements per RFID tag. Firstly, a benchmark test to evaluate the healthy status of the tag before irradiation, to be used later as a reference. Secondly, measurements after each of the three radiation steps. Lastly, one measurement after several weeks to evaluate the recovery capacity of the tag.

As Figure 13 shows, Tables 2 and 3 also show no degradation for the first two irradiation steps in both tags. The damage is produced after the third dose.

On one hand, tag 805F received an excessive dose of over 2000 Gy, and no recovery is observed afterwards. But on the other hand, tag 805C received a dose much closer to the failure threshold, and after two weeks of irradiation it recovered part of its functionalities.

Tag 805C recovered fully the memory reading functionalities. But memory writing is non functional and the detection range has been degraded. Regarding the degradation of the detection range, the tag used to be read at distance step number four, but after recovery it is not anymore detectable at this position. Also the signal strength measured at all the other distance steps is weaker.

ID	Dose (Gy)	Acc. Dose (Gy)	Timestamp Start	Timestamp End
805F	10.98	10.98	15/10/2021 11:42:33	15/10/2021 11:42:33
805F	113.98	124.01	15/10/2021 12:34:15	15/10/2021 12:39:07
805F	2071.27	2195.28	15/10/2021 12:40:08	15/10/2021 15:37:38
805C	10.94	10.94	26/10/2021 18:09:33	26/10/2021 18:09:33
805C	101.99	112.93	26/10/2021 18:45:43	26/10/2021 18:54:22
805C	202.58	315.51	26/10/2021 19:52:28	26/10/2021 20:01:19

Table 1. RFID tag irradiation’s start time, end time, step, and accumulated absorbed dose of ionizing radiation.

ID	Timestamp	Acc. Dose (Gy)	Antenna OK	Altered Bits	Reading OK	Writing OK
805F	14/10/2021 17:36:00	0	TRUE	0	TRUE	TRUE
805F	15/10/2021 11:42:33	10.98	TRUE	0	TRUE	TRUE
805F	15/10/2021 12:34:15	124.01	TRUE	0	TRUE	TRUE
805F	15/10/2021 12:40:08	2195.28	FALSE	-	-	-
805F	10/11/2021 10:15:00	2195.28	FALSE	-	-	-
805C	26/10/2021 17:05:00	0	TRUE	0	TRUE	TRUE
805C	26/10/2021 18:19:00	10.94	TRUE	0	TRUE	TRUE
805C	26/10/2021 19:12:00	112.93	TRUE	0	TRUE	TRUE
805C	26/10/2021 20:10:00	315.51	FALSE	-	-	-
805C	10/11/2021 10:00:00	315.51	TRUE	0	TRUE	FALSE

Table 2. RFID measurements (1/2). RFID tag irradiation accumulated absorbed dose of ionizing radiation, antenna, memory integrity, reading and writing checks.

ID	Timestamp	Acc. Dose (Gy)	Step 0	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5
805F	14/10/2021 17:36:00	0	425	545	565	625	-	-
805F	15/10/2021 11:42:33	10.98	425	545	565	605	-	-
805F	15/10/2021 12:34:15	124.01	425	545	565	605	-	-
805F	15/10/2021 12:40:08	2195.28	-	-	-	-	-	-
805F	10/11/2021 10:15:00	2195.28	-	-	-	-	-	-
805C	26/10/2021 17:05:00	0	425	545	565	605	625	-
805C	26/10/2021 18:19:00	10.94	425	525	565	605	625	-
805C	26/10/2021 19:12:00	112.93	425	545	565	605	625	-
805C	26/10/2021 20:10:00	315.51	-	-	-	-	-	-
805C	10/11/2021 10:00:00	315.51	445	505	565	625	-	-

Table 3. RFID measurements (2/2). RFID tag irradiation accumulated absorbed dose of ionizing radiation and maximum absolute RSSI per distance step.

5 Conclusions

There are three conclusions from this study. First, RFID tags with chip U7-XM2 are resistant up to 100 Gy and failure threshold resides between 100 and 316 Gy. Second, proton irradiation results are consistent with previous gamma irradiation study performed by CAEN S.r.l. Third, partial recovery of tags is possible for doses closer to failure threshold. Recovered tag wasn't in perfect condition, it had a total loss of writing capabilities, a partial loss of detection range and partial loss of signal strength across all distance steps.

6 Future Work

Five future work paths have been identified for this project. First, carry proton irradiations with the two remaining available chips and perform damage and recovery assessments. Second, irradiate tags using higher proton beam intensities to see if failure threshold is reduced. Third, modify setup to be able to perform active measurement of tags during irradiations. Fourth, irradiate tags with additional beam types, such as neutrons, gamma,

electrons and muons. Fifth and last, include in studies spectroscopy analysis of irradiated tags.

7 Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under GA no 101004761.

References

- [1] F. Ravotti, B. Gkotse, M. Glaser, P. Jouvelot, I.M. Mateu, V. Meskova, G. Pezzullo, and J.M. Sallese. The IRRAD Proton Irradiation Facility Control, Data Management and Beam Diagnostic Systems: An Outlook of the Major Upgrades Beyond the CERN Long Shutdown 2. In *Proc. ICALEPCS'19*, number 17 in International Conference on Accelerator and Large Experimental Physics Control Systems, pages 1389–1393. JACoW Publishing, Geneva, Switzerland, 08 2020. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-ICALEPCS2019-WEPHA127>.
- [2] ALIEN. Higgs 3 datasheet. <https://www.alientechnology.com/wp-content/uploads/ALC-360%20Higgs3%202014-12-21.pdf>, November 2021.
- [3] IMPINJ. Monza 4 datasheet. https://support.impinj.com/hc/article_attachments/4409894434323/Impinj_Monza_4_Tag_Chip_Datasheet_20211020.pdf, November 2021.
- [4] WINTAG. U7-xm2 datasheet. <https://www.wintag.it/wp-content/uploads/wpallimport/files/EN-DS%20TU-02xm2%20UHF%20Label%20Wintag.pdf>, November 2021.
- [5] CAEN RFID. Hex multipurpose rain rfid reader with poe – technical information manual. https://www.caenrfid.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/R1290I_Hex_Technical-Information-Manual_Rev_03.pdf, November 2021.
- [6] CAEN RFID. Easy controller – software user interface for caen rfid readers. https://www.caenrfid.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Easy-Controller-Software_Technical-Information-Manual_rev-05.pdf, November 2021.
- [7] CAEN RFID. Caen rfid easy controller software – technical information manual. https://www.caenrfid.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/EasyController_Technical-Information-Manual_rev-04.pdf, November 2021.
- [8] Federico Ravotti Ferdinando Giordano. Private communication, July 2021.